

PML

Plymouth Marine
Laboratory

Research excellence supporting a sustainable ocean

Constructing Digital Environments; Generating FAIR data from high resolution sensors in the Western Channel Observatory

Architecture design & requirements
elicitation workshop 2

15th May 2023 | v1.1

2nd External Workshop; Welcome!

- Today marks the half-way point in the elapsed time of the project.
- This in mind, this workshop aims to:
 - *Provide demonstrations of the interfaces and applications developed in the first development sprints.*
 - *Provide an overview of the proposed data pipelines that the new interfaces could support.*
 - *Discuss potential next steps and collect feedback that will inform activities in the next development sprints.*

Project Status

- 6 month project
- £42 K budget
- Three deliverables (*D1, D2 and D3*)
- Due to complete 31st July 2023

Outputs from Workshop 1 (29th Mar '23)

	Topic	Workshop Output	Status Summary	Notes
Intro & Project Progress	Data Users	Opportunity to collect feedback from non-academic users	In progress	We're currently reviewing opportunities to discuss the developments with PML's place-based engagement teams.
		Investigate adding features that allow users to provide rapid/less formal feedback (e.g. problem with data sets or problems with the website)	Complete	To be demonstrated in this workshop
Epic User Stories	Metadata	Opportunity to better define the data granularity and the structure of each URI	Complete	Updated definition to be discussed further as part of this workshop
		Clarify where best to associate metadata and discovery metadata within the data analysis tool	Complete	To be demonstrated in this workshop
		Opportunity to further encourage the use of controlled vocabularies and parameter names	Complete	To be demonstrated in this workshop
Demo Data Viz. MVP	Additional Capabilities	Expand the use of the new data visualisation tools to the composite data	Complete	To be demonstrated in this workshop
		Improve the integration of metadata with the data visualisation tools	In progress	Updated metadata appears in data request forms. Plot metadata still to be updated.
		Continue the planned development activities to meet the Measures of Success	In progress	Inputs into sprint 3 are welcome!
Develop Ticketing MVP				
Discussion & next steps				

Project aims and objectives

- As stated in the project proposal, the aims and objectives of this project are:

Project aims and objectives;

What is the challenge we're trying to solve?

Epic user story 1:

“As an external data user, I’d like to explore the WCO CTD data parameters so that I can find and access the data I need to progress my scientific objectives.”

Project aims and objectives;

What is the challenge we're trying to solve?

Intro & Project Progress

Epic User Stories

Demo Data Viz. MVP

Develop Ticketing MVP

Discussion & next steps

Epic user story 2:

“As a data contributor, I'd like to receive feedback about the value and quality of the CTD data that we're collecting so that we can maximise the value of future data collection in emerging digital environments.”

Project aims and objectives;

What is the challenge we're trying to solve?

Epic user story 3:

“As a data contributor, I'd like to know who is using the CTD data and what they're using it for so that I can maximise the value of future data collection in emerging digital environments.”

Project aims and objectives; What is the challenge we're trying to solve?

Intro & Project Progress

Epic User Stories

Demo Data Viz. MVP

Develop Ticketing MVP

Discussion & next steps

Epic user story 4:

“As an external data user, I’d like to be guided through the process of finding and accessing the CTD data I need so that I can reuse it in my project.”

Qualitative assessment: The project's FAIR impact

		F	A	I	R
<p>Intro & Project Progress</p> <p>Epic User Stories</p> <p>Demo Data Viz. MVP</p> <p>Develop Ticketing MVP</p> <p>Discussion & next steps</p>	<p>Epic User Story 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased visibility and clarity of metadata within intuitive tools, makes its meaning more explicit for end users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased visibility of key metadata fields. - Elements of data access framework standardised; potential to share requests among providers and DACs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased emphasis on metadata quality with data contributors allows incorporation into external portals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased emphasis on metadata quality is a foundation for automated data recovery. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased emphasis on metadata quality with data encourages the use of standard tools (e.g. NVS)
	<p>Epic User Story 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information collected will allow assessment of community portals to be made. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information collected that will allow impact reporting to better understand who access data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information collected will allow assessment of community vocabularies to be made. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability for users to report data quality issues so that the data provider can take action. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability for users to report data quality issues so that the data provider can take action.
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Data Visualisations; Proposed workflows

Data Visualisations; Sprint 2 Update Demonstration

Intro & workshop aims

Epic User Stories

Demo Data Viz. MVP

Develop Ticketing MVP

Discussion & next steps

Links provided to support the user through data access steps.

Intuitive tools allow users to explore multiple data sets to fully understand their content.

Live demonstration of developed features to be presented in the workshop

Associated MEDIN standard discovery metadata displayed

Discovery metadata auto-populated from data pipeline toolsets

Automated data quality checking highlights potential data issues in intuitive manner.

Metadata displayed in interactive tools; encouraging the improvement of metadata and the use of standards at creation.

Ability for users to provide further quick feedback

Improved representation of data quality issues / missing data

Temperature (°C)

Salinity (PSU)

Fluorescence (V)

Depth (m)

Unique Resource Identifier: 131217_L4.asc

Resource Language: eng (English)

Topic category: oceans

Keywords: Sea Water Salinity

How is our data looking?
Select a smiley & frowny type here...

Data Visualisations; Discussion Points & Opportunities for Sprint 3

- Work to further standardise the underlying metadata and discovery metadata.
- Improved workflow from data visualisation to data request.
- Improved explanation and transparency of the automated data quality checking processes.
- Improved capabilities to combine data from different data sets.
- More intuitive links between viewed data and their location within available datasets.
- **More suggestions welcome!**

Data Request Ticketing; Proposed workflows

Data Request Ticketing; Sprint 2 Update Demonstration

Live demonstration of developed features to be presented in the workshop

Intro & workshop aims
Epic User Stories
Demo Data Viz. MVP
Develop Ticketing MVP
Dis...

Home Data Publications Webcams About us Contact us

Custom Data Request Form

User Details

*Name: Ben O'Driscoll

*Email: bod@wco.ac.uk

*Organisation: PML

Department: EOSA

Sector:

- Academia
- Industry
- Government
- NGO
- Media

Project Details

Project Title: Temperature Variation in Plymouth Sound between 2010-2020

Project Type:

- Undergraduate
- Masters
- PhD
- Industry
- Commissioned Project
- Scientific Paper
- Policy Relevant Report
- Other

Data Details

*Start Date: 01/01/2010

*End Date: 31/12/2019

*Measurement:

- Temperature(°C) at Depth (m)
- Salinity(PSU) at Depth (m)
- Density(Kgm-3) at Depth (m)
- Transmission at Depth (m)
- PAR (µEm-2s-1) or Turbidity (NTU) at Depth (m)
- Chl a at Depth (m)

*Site:

- L4 Pelagic
- L4 Atmospheric
- L4 Buoy
- L4 within 1 km of Buoy
- L4 benthic
- L4 benthic at Hilmar's Box

Additional Details

Report Outcome:

- Report
- Thesis
- Conference Proceeding, Journal Paper, Book
- Decision Making Exercise
- Policy Advice
- Other

Data collected that allows the likely impact of the data to be assessed.

Current metadata values used, encouraging the adoption of standards-based terms for the measured parameters.

Current metadata values used, encouraging the adoption of standards-based terms for the site.

Guidance provided to encourage the correct and consistent citation of the data.

Automated notifications sent to data points of contact (POC's)

Additional Details

User Notices

- We kindly request that all data uptake is appropriately acknowledged a... Data Policy of the NERC National Capability funded Western... delivery. However, we request that prospective data use... provide the metadata, the most up... data can be used. We expect...
- By clicking submit, you consent to allow Plymouth Marine Laboratory to make the data freely available at the... points of contact at PML, before obtaining the...

[Privacy Policy](#)

Reset

WCO Data Request Form

wcorequestform@gmail.com

To: Ben O'Driscoll, Thomas Mansfield

[WARNING] This message comes from an external organization. Please check sender details, links and attachments

WCO_ID	12
Form Submitted	12/05/2023_09:22:28
Name	Ben O'Driscoll
Email	bod@wco.ac.uk
Organisation	PML
Department	EOSA
Project Title	Temperature Variation in Plymouth Sound
Project Description	Postgraduate project investigating the temperature change in Plymouth Sound between 2010-2020
Start Date	2010-01-01
End Date	2019-12-31
Measurement	CTD
Site	L4

Data Request Ticketing; Discussion Points & Opportunities for Sprint 3

- Work to further standardise the underlying metadata and discovery metadata.
- PML GDPR workshop to be held (Scheduled 25th May) to ensure compliance of the design and implementation.
- Investigate the ability to send requests to BODC for datasets archived there.
 - May include the use of automated data request processes (to be discussed)
- How to incorporate direct data request from the visualisation pages
- **More suggestions welcome!**

Summary: Current Status

2 development sprints developed a tailored visualization that emphasizes metadata, discovery metadata and data quality.

Project Objective 1 – Make data findable with scalable and tailored data visualization

Project Aim - Use FAIR data principles to maximize the impact of new, high resolution marine sensing technologies

Project Objective 2 - Ticketing system to improve data access and impact monitoring

Progress made against many (not all) FAIR principles

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2 development sprints developed a data request form and associated back end.

Summary: Likely next steps

Thanks for your time!

Spare slide(s)

Data flow to BODC (Draft v0.1)

The role of the Excel-based catalogue (Draft v0.1)

